

Effectiveness of Scamper Based Module in Learning Literature Among Grade 11-ABM Students

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learning literature, intervention, module, pretest, posttest

Abstract. The goal of this quasi-experimental research was to establish a causal relationship between independent and dependent variables. This research aimed to assess the effectiveness of the Scamper-Based Module, developed by the researcher, in enhancing the learning of literature among Grade 11-ABM students. The module served as an intervention to improve students' proficiency in English literature. The research instruments included the developed module, pretest, formative test, and posttest questionnaire. Mean scores were used as statistical tools to calculate the participants' learning literature performance in the pretest, formative test, and posttest. The paired T test was employed to compare the mean scores before and after exposure to the Scamper-Based Module. The findings indicated a rejection of the null hypothesis, which suggested no significant difference between the mean scores of formative tests in students' learning literature in the two groups during exposure to the Scamper-Based Module. The participants are composed of 15 students per group. Comparing the pretest and posttest mean scores of the two groups with different approaches revealed a significant increase in English literature proficiency among learners exposed to the module. The results demonstrated that students who received the intervention through the Scamper Based Module showed improvement in their learning literature compared to those who did not receive the intervention. Based on these findings, it can be concluded that the Scamper-Based Module is effective in enhancing the learning literature of Grade 11-ABM students. The teachers may consider enhancing the literature learning competency of senior high school students by exploring frameworks that will guide them in teaching literature.

Introduction

To ensure that students understand literature, instructional practices should be implemented and studied. "The SCAMPER Strategy" is one of the tactics that allows learners to come up with new or alternative ideas. It is a tool that promotes creative and varied thinking. SCAMPER is an acronym for substitute, combine, adapt, modify, magnify, minimize, repurpose, remove, and reverse/rearrange. SCAMPER helps students ask questions that force them to think "beyond the lines" of a text. As such, it helps them develop critical thinking abilities and create their own inventive texts. It is a great role-playing stimulus and a useful cooperative learning tool (A-Z Learning Strategy). According to Jensen and Scharff (2019), students tend to benefit best from the method when they have had some time to read a text.

The learning of students is facilitated and monitored by the teachers; they are the ones who impart knowledge to the students in a variety of areas. They also teach the students how to complete specific tasks in a creative manner. They come up with methods for efficiently delivering the lesson and utilizing various techniques to make it more engaging. Teaching strategy is crucial to helping students grasp literature. It is necessary to introduce the process of this progress in a straightforward manner. Teaching literature may be a challenging and stressful endeavor for some teachers because the subject is not only vast but also demands deeper comprehension and critical analysis for the students to fully grasp the entire work (Ugwu, 2022). To be able to do this, the improvement of reading skills should be acquired by the students, as it is a very important factor in understanding literature. It helps the students comprehend and interpret a text, and most importantly, it can help them understand literature further.

Moreover, literature is divided into two categories: prose and poetry. Prose can be either fiction or nonfiction. Shorter than a novel, a short story is a fictional prose tale that targets unity of effect, usually involves a small number of characters, and frequently concentrates more on mood setting than on storyline. It is difficult to comprehend the short story. It combines reading comprehension and critical thinking, both of which can be strengthened by the teacher. It is the teacher's responsibility to assist the students in appreciating the worth of literature by implementing instructional practices that greatly enhance the students' cognitive and emotional development (Allen & Kelly 2018).

Reading and analyzing short stories is a must for all students, even those in senior high school, because understanding a short tale requires critical analysis and comprehension. Doing this can aid students in growing their critical thinking skills because short story analysis calls for neat, ordered, and organized writing. It can also be beneficial for the students to be systematic. Most of all, it can help them to be good individuals because in every story there are lessons and values that they can apply in real life. There are many strategies that can be helpful not only for the teacher but also for the student to understand and appreciate a short story, for them to discover, to think, and to be creative in analyzing a short story.

The argument for this study is anchored in the challenge of teaching literature to students in specialized strands like Accountancy, Business, and Management (ABM), who often perceive the subject as secondary to their core technical competencies. Current scholarship emphasizes that literature is not merely a collection of stories but a tool for developing high-level analytical skills essential for real-world problem solving. However, there remains a gap in practical, theory-driven interventions that successfully translate abstract literary analysis into the creative, systematic thinking preferred by business students. This study addresses this gap by testing the SCAMPER strategy as a modular intervention.

This study is conceptualized through the Reader-Response Theory. Mart (2019) posits that literature is a reciprocal relationship between the text and the reader's perceptions. By utilizing SCAMPER, students are not passive recipients of meaning but active creators who manipulate literary elements—substituting characters or reversing plots—to construct new understanding. This aligns with Constructivism, where learners build new knowledge by building upon prior experiences through active inquiry.

Additionally, it is important for accounting and business management students to delve into literature's beauty because doing so will not only help them unwind after a tough day at school but will also help them develop their analytical skills. Every time they read a story, they feel like they have a duty to evaluate or summarize it. Similar to accounting, they need a bigger imagination to come up with solutions. In some cases, students become more driven and engaged when they achieve something, such as passing midterms or finals. By achieving these goals, students are inspired to tell others about how they feel and what they have done, which encourages them to create their own stories (WD Albrecht, 2018). The researcher wanted to find out the result of the Effectiveness of SCAMPER Based Module in learning literature among Grade 11-ABM students of Looc Integrated School SY:2023-2024 if this strategy is appropriate to the respondents and that if they can appreciate more the significance of literature.

Methodology

Research Design

This chapter discusses the research design, respondents of the study, population sampling, research instrument and validation, data gathering procedure, and statistical treatment of the study.

To achieve the purpose of this study, a quantitative research design was used. The method used in this study was the quasi-experimental method. The experimental technique, according to Ariola (2006), is a statistical research method that involves manipulating one or more variables as well as measuring the consequences of such manipulation on behavior. She defined it as a process used to discover unknown information and determine the origin of a phenomenon. She also stated that experiments are systematic observations used to discover cause and effect correlations and are a useful method for producing reliable behavioral descriptions.

The experimental method was applicable in this study because the researcher aims to know the effectiveness of the SCAMPER-Based Module in learning literature among Grade 11-ABM students of Looc Integrated School. In order to determine if the experiment was effective on the experimental group, the pretest and posttest results of two groups were compared. This type of experimental design was considered a quasi-experimental design since it was done within a short period of time (Moore, 2008).

Participants and Sampling Technique

The study was participated in by Grade 11 students that were enrolled in Looc Integrated School. Participants in the study were 32 grade 11-ABM students from Drucker and Weber of Looc Integrated School, class 2023-2024. To obtain a more

accurate and dependable basis of information, the researcher used 16 students per section as her participants. The population of the participants in the study was 11-Drucker, which is composed of 16 students, and 16 students from Weber, for a total of 32 students.

PARTICIPANTS	POPULATION	PERCENTAGE
11-DRUCKER	16	50%
11- WEBER	16	50%
Total	32	100%

Research Instrument

The efficacy of the SCAMPER-Based Module in Literature Learning was the main topic of this research. The SCAMPER-Based Module was employed by the researcher to instruct literature. Additionally, the pre- and posttest results were utilized to determine how well the created module worked for Grade 11 ABM students' comprehension levels. The two pieces of literature that the researcher used to apply the SCAMPER strategy comprised the material from the pretest and posttests. The works of literature are Amador Daguio's *The Wedding Dance* and Manuel Arguilla's *How My Brother Leon Brought Home a Wife*.

The researcher collected data based on observation and adapted a selfmade module in the application of the intervention, wherein the researcher provided a vocabulary exercise before reading the given literature, then provided a table wherein the students were given ideas of the following steps in the Scamper Strategy: substitute (a person, place, time, or situation), wherein the learners were provide specific alteration of the scenario in the given literature. Combine (bring together assorted ideas and situations), wherein the learners combined two or more ideas together to change a specific scenario in the given literature. Adapt (or adjust to suit a purpose), wherein the learners adapt a scenario from a different literature and use that in the given literature. Modify (for example, by changing the physical size or personality traits of some characters or changing the setting), wherein the learners changed the characteristics of the character as well as the given setting in the literature. Put to other uses (for example, put a different slant on the plot), wherein the learners changed the plot according to what they wanted. Eliminate a feature of the story, wherein the learners' removed scenarios in the story to make it more interesting. And lastly, rearrange or reverse the sequence of the story, wherein learners have the opportunity to change the sequence of events in the given literature.

A self-made pretest and posttest questionnaire were used during and after the intervention of the Scamper based Module for the student participants undergone for validation. After drafting the questions and creating the worksheets to be used for the intervention, the validation of the research instruments was done together with 3 experts in the field of teaching; all had taught English for more than 5 years. The experts were selected based on criteria such as (1) having taught English for more than 5 years, (2) having handled and taught senior high school students and bachelor's degree major in English, and (3) having a master's degree. The researcher prepared printed copies of the research instruments together with the validating tool to be used; each validator received a copy of the research instruments. Furthermore, the researcher secured the validating tool with the criteria of the following: For the Worksheet Development Criteria, the researcher used five criteria which are Functional Worksheet, Instructional Objectives, Assessments, Instructional Activities, and Audience Appropriateness. For the Pretest and Posttest validation tool the researcher used five criteria as well which are Clarity, Wordiness, Overlapping Responses, Balance, and Use of Jargons. The validating tool were signed by the validators with their feedback. Based on the validator's comments and feedback, the questions were appropriate for the level of the students. The questions were simple and specific and could be answered by the students.

The overall validation results for SCAMPER-Based Module Learning Material are based on five criteria indicators: functional worksheet, instructional objectives, assessments, instructional activities, and audience appropriateness of the module. The weighted mean for each criterion is 4.00 and 4.33, respectively. The results indicated that the SCAMPER-based module was highly valid in terms of content and structure, presentation of the module, and usefulness of the module, with a total score of 4.10. It only suggested that the validation process be thorough, comprehensive, and concise, resulting in reliable and valid results. This revealed that the activities in the module were effective in enhancing the reading comprehension skills of the senior high school students.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher sought the permission of the Schools Division Office of Calamba City to conduct the study. A letter of intent was sent to the school head of Looc Integrated School. She discussed the objectives and the process of the study.

The researcher conducted the pretest with the comparison and experimental groups; after that, the researcher used the Scamper-based module for the experimental group and the traditional method for the comparison group.

After the retrieval of the formative test, pretest, and posttest, the researcher asked for the assistance of the assigned statistician for statistical treatment, analysis, and interpretation of the data. To gather additional information related to the study, the researcher used the internet and visited the library at LSPU.

Data Analysis Procedure

The researchers used non-probability sampling, specifically purposive sampling, to obtain the sample. According to Reyes (2004), the purposive sampling technique is a type of non-probability sampling that is most effective when one needs to study a certain cultural domain with knowledgeable experts within. The purposive sampling technique allowed for a more targeted and efficient selection process, ensuring that the sample was representative of the population of interest. It involves intentionally selecting individuals who possess specific characteristics or traits relevant to the research objective. The selection of the sample was done by considering the academic strand of the respondents, which is the ABM grade level and section. Thus, students in Grade 11 ABM Drucker and Grade 11 ABM Weber at Looc Integrated School were selected.

Ethical Considerations

Throughout the course of this study, the researcher regarded ethical principles as a primary consideration. Before administering the Scamper Based Module to the Grade 11 students, the researcher sought the permission of the school principal and the participants' adviser. The researcher also handed out a consent form for participation to the respondents to confirm that they were voluntarily participating in the study. The letter of participation includes a detailed description of the study's purpose, the administration of the pretest and posttest, and the use of the Scamper Based Module. Most importantly, the data gathered were used for research purposes only.

Results and Discussion

Remarkably, both groups have identical pretest statistics, with mean scores and standard deviations expressed as (5.63 ± 2.47) . The descriptive interpretation for these scores is labeled as "Low," suggesting that, on average, participants in both groups demonstrated low reading comprehension skills before any experimental interventions or comparison conditions were applied. This parity in pretest scores indicates that the groups were equivalently matched regarding their initial reading comprehension abilities, establishing a reliable baseline for assessing the impacts of subsequent experimental or comparative analyses within the study.

The experimental group had a higher mean score than the comparison group, indicating that the intervention might have been effective in enhancing the experimental group's Reading Comprehension Skill through the SCAMPER-based module learning material. Overall, both groups performed very well on the formative test, with the experimental group showing a greater improvement than the comparison group.

The efficaciousness of the SCAMPER strategy employed in the literature learning material could potentially account for the higher mean scores of the experimental group. Through the module's exercises, students were able to replace, combine, adapt, modify, magnify, minimize, put to other purposes, remove, reverse, and rearrange scenarios in the provided material. The exercises help students pose inquiries that push them to consider ideas "beyond the lines" of a text.

As a result, it facilitates the growth of their critical thinking abilities and helps them produce original works of fiction. It is a helpful tool for cooperative learning and a great role-playing stimulus (A-Z Learning Strategy). The aforementioned exercises frequently yield the best results after students have had some time to study the book (Jensen, M., & Scharff, L. 2019). It is exactly what Creely (2019) suggested. He said that these guiding principles provided a basis for teaching literature because of its close connections to human interaction. This provided a means of facilitating effective literature education within initiatives and teaching customs.

Furthermore, as stated by Spirovska (2019), when characterizing the connection between the audience and the text, The text affects the reader's comprehension and perceptions. The information is written with the reader in mind. The reader-response theory, according to Mart (2019), is based on the premises of the text and assumes that there is a reciprocal relationship between the readership and the literary work. Georgiou et al. (2023) state that good analytical skills include the following: "explain," "analyze," "synthesize," "argue," "interpret," "evaluate," "solve problems," "infer," "reason logically," and "to apply." Reading comprehension skills can be enhanced through a series of practices and providing activities that let the student think beyond the text. This was a helpful tool for them, which reflected some of the activities and strategies used in the module.

The experimental group recorded a mean score of (16.31 ± 2.87) , which is interpreted descriptively as "High." This suggests a notable improvement in the reading comprehension abilities of the experimental group participants, likely attributable to the educational intervention they received. Conversely, the comparison group, which presumably did not undergo the same intervention, achieved a mean score of (9.38 ± 2.87) , classified as "Low." This significant discrepancy in posttest scores between the two groups highlights the effectiveness of the intervention implemented with the experimental group in enhancing reading comprehension skills.

Based on these findings, it may be concluded that the Experimental Group outperformed the Comparison Group on the posttest of Literature Learning. The experimental intervention had a favorable influence on the Experimental Group's Literature learning when compared to the Comparison Group. Further analysis is needed to determine the relative performance of the two groups on the posttest in English proficiency.

According to Nardo (2019), using modules promotes independence as well. study. It instructs students to practice or memorize the material. Exercises are provided for the concepts to be mastered. Following the order of easy to difficult activities. The way the exercises are set up establishes the maximum level of difficulty that students can perform. A further advantage of using modules for instruction is the development of better selfstudy or learning skills among students. Students become more involved in understanding the concepts presented in the module, feel more responsible for completing the tasks assigned to them, and make progress on their own with little to no help from the teacher. They are empowered.

The mean score for the experimental group is recorded at (12.44) . The analysis unveils a significant mean difference between the groups, marked at (2.94) . This disparity is further evidenced by a t-value of $(2.845 **)$, where the double asterisks (**) typically signify a statistically significant difference, suggesting a p-value below a conventional threshold like 0.05 or 0.01, although the exact value is not specified here.

Moreover, the effect size, measured by Cohen's d, is (1.06) , categorized as "Huge." Cohen's d is a unitless measure of effect size that provides insight into the magnitude of the difference between two means in terms of standard deviations.

An effect size of (1.06) is considered substantial, indicating that the intervention or educational methodology applied to the experimental group had a significant and meaningful impact on their formative test outcomes in reading comprehension.

The t-value and Cohen's d collectively offer a comprehensive view of the analysis: the t-value establishes the statistical significance of the mean difference, assuring that the observed disparity is not merely a product of random variation. Cohen's d, on the other hand, quantifies the practical significance of this difference, shedding light on the actual impact of the intervention in a real-world context.

In the realm of educational research, findings of significant and sizable effects are particularly valuable as they suggest the potential effectiveness of specific teaching strategies, materials, or learning environments. For the Grade 11 ABM students involved in this study, the notable improvement in the experimental group's performance could reflect successful educational practices that may be beneficial for broader application or further investigation within similar educational settings.

The statistical significance of this mean difference is underscored by a tvalue of $(6.836 **)$, where the double asterisks (**) suggest a high level of significance, likely indicating a p-value much less than conventional thresholds (e.g., 0.01 or 0.05). This high t-value points to a very low probability that the observed difference in mean scores is due to random chance, thus indicating a significant effect of the intervention or conditions applied to the experimental group.

Moreover, the effect size, as measured by Cohen's d, is (2.42) , classified as "Huge." This value denotes a substantial difference in effect size, suggesting that the intervention had a profound impact on the reading comprehension abilities of the students in the experimental group compared to those in the comparison group. An effect size of this magnitude is particularly noteworthy in educational research, as it indicates that the interventions or methodologies employed have led to significant improvements in student outcomes, warranting further exploration or adoption in similar educational contexts.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the major findings of the study, the researcher was able to derive the following conclusions:

The hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference between the formative test mean scores of the experimental and comparison groups after the administration of the intervention was rejected.

The hypothesis asserting that there is no significant difference between the posttest results of the experimental and comparison groups after the administration of the intervention was rejected.

The hypothesis that there is no significant difference between the pretest and posttest results of the students after exposure to the SCAMPER-Based Module material was rejected.

Lastly, based on the pretest and posttest mean scores of the comparison and experimental groups, it can be concluded that the SCAMPER Based module has proven its effectiveness in enhancing the Grade 11-ABM Senior High School students' reading comprehension skills.

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Competing Interests Statement

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this article.

Data Availability Statement

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new data were created or analyzed in this study; all data used were obtained from previously published sources as cited in the reference list.

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Appendices

No appendices are attached to this study.